

USE OF MODERN METHODS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article describes some of the ways to teach English effectively, as well as some of the modern teaching technologies used in language learning.

Keywords: Language, English, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

By the end of the twentieth century, the status of English as a language of global importance was finally strengthened. Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of vocational education. Specialists in various fields have a high level of cooperation with foreign partners, so they have a high demand for language learning. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of vocational education. Such knowledge is first acquired by people in schools, colleges, high schools, and later in institutes, training courses, or by familiarizing themselves with basic information sets that help them learn a foreign language independently. The research used popular methods of teaching and learning English, as well as Internet resources. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical-deductive reasoning, analysis and synthesis, logic were used. Language is the main means of communication, without which it is difficult to imagine the existence and development of human society. At a time of great changes in social relations in our world today, communication media (information technology) requires students to improve their communication skills, to exchange ideas in different situations in the process of interaction with other participants in communication, language and so on. requires the correct use of the norms of conciliation. In such an environment, the main goal of a foreign language is to form communicative ability, i.e. to implement interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language. By the end of the twentieth century, the status of English as a language of global importance was finally strengthened. In most schools around the world, learning it has become mandatory, and teaching methods have begun to evolve with leaps and bounds. Not everyone has the opportunity to attend courses that led to the emergence of the first method of independent learning of English. Later, many authors tried to create an effective program of learning English independently, but we will focus on the 4 most popular.

1. Shexter method

This method of learning English is based on a reverse, more natural system of cognition, rather than a classical model of 'theory to practice'. It's very similar to how we learn our native language. The author gives an example of how young children learn to speak - after all, no one explains to them the rules of constructing sentences, situations and parts of speech. Similarly, Igor Yuryevich Shekhter suggests learning English. The essence of the modern method of learning English is that from the first lesson students are given a specific task, for example, to learn the profession of the interlocutor. In addition, all students play what are called "études," where they act in different roles and try to solve a problem. Because communication takes place between people with approximately the same level of language proficiency, the fear of using foreign speech that arises in communication between teacher and student disappears. This technique of English consists of three stages: in the first stage lexical units, words and phrases are given, and only in the second and third stages the use of grammatical and syntactic structures is corrected. The system has proven its effectiveness several times and is currently one of the most successful from the point of view of pedagogical psychologists.

2. Pimsler method

Dr. Paul Pimsler developed a special system of thirty-minute lessons designed not only to perceive information but also to reproduce it. Each lesson is taught by two people: our compatriot and a native English speaker. Thanks to this and special memorization technology, each student learns hundreds of words and phrases in English for each lesson. The essence of the lesson is to do a series of assignments told by the speakers. The undoubted advantages of the technique include its mobility - you can perform audio tasks anywhere: when you're in a traffic jam, on your way to work, on the subway on your way to a meeting, or in bed before bed. The downside will be the lack of a high-quality pronunciation and knowledge acquisition test.

3. Petrov method

Dmitry Petrov says you can learn English in 16 hours. True, the author once again makes it clear that we are talking about basic knowledge, not about mastering the language at the level of a citizen born in the UK. Her lessons are enough to help you survive in an English-speaking environment, explain your needs, and understand the answer.

Modern language teaching is aimed at forming a more cultured individual who has the skills to self-analyze and systematize new knowledge. Innovative

methods are an integral part of modernizing the entire system. In this way, teachers can become acquainted with the most advanced approaches and then combine them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level, using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the whole educational process. Adequate attention should be paid to the development of speaking skills and social resilience in training. In addition, the success of any lesson in education depends in many ways on the proper organization of the lesson. The lesson should be based on the creative collaboration of teacher and student. Only then will students be able to think independently and develop their will.

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